

High Precision Digital Phase Meter

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The objective of this paper is to describe the design of a wide-bandwidth, noise-resistant digital phase meter. The principle of the design is based on phase compensation while the phase shifter is digitally controlled is the main core of the paper and is described in detail. The design is accurate for more the -6 dB signal to noise ratios,

I. INTRODUCTION

The need for measuring the sinusoidal signal phase difference in the presence of noise is encountered in many systems; for example, in distance measuring equipment. Although the optimal algorithm is well established [1] it is difficult to implement in practice as it involves multiplication of two sinusoidal signals. Analogue multiplication is not precise enough, while digital multiplication with pre-ceding analogue/digital conversion limits the upper frequency of operation. Therefore, many suboptimal systems, including the so-called compensative phase meter, have been proposed [2]-[7]. An analogue realization of this phase meter has been described in [8]. This paper presents a digital realization of this device. The described instrument produces unbiased estimates of the measured phase independent of the noise level at the input [5]. However, the variance of the estimate is slightly greater than that of the optimal algorithm. This increase may reach 29 percent at maximum [10].

II. OPERATING PRINCIPLE

A block diagram of the device is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of Changes in an XOR gate, an up-down counter, a demultiplexer, a pulse generator, a frequency divider, two limiters, and a controlled phase shifter. Impulses from the generator are fed to the counter, which counts up or down depending on the output signal of the XOR gate. In the steady state the signals at the inputs of the gate are shifted by 90° as the number of impulses counted up and down are equal in this case. If this phase shift was different from 90° the mean number in the counter would change, varying the phase shift of the controlled phase shifter to compensate for this inequality. In this way, the number in the counter directly expresses the measured phase shift increased or decreased by 90°. This is also true in the presence of heavy noise interference in the signal channel because the mean numbers of impulses are counted up and down.

are equal for the shifted by 90° input signals, independent of the noise level.

The concrete realization of the digitally controlled phase shifter and the counter determines the difference ($\pm 90^\circ$) between the actual phase shift and the controlling number from the counter. Only one position is stable for a given realization [4].

It may be shown that in the absence of noise, the phase error γ between the indication (with the 90° phase shift taken into account) and the actual phase difference is given by [5].

$$\gamma = \gamma_0 e^{-(2/\tau)}$$

where γ_0 is an initial phase shift and

$$\tau = \frac{2^{r-2}}{fg}$$

Here fg is the generator frequency, τ is the number of bits controlling the phase shifter, and K is the frequency division ratio $K = 512$. The time constant τ is proportional to the frequency division ratio K as increasing of K gives slower changes in the counter that controls the phase shifter. In the same way, the value of τ is inversely proportional to the frequency fg as increasing of fg speeds up changes in this counter. Based on [5] we can approximate the mean square error of indications σ_γ^2 in the presence of noise. We have high and moderate values of the signal power to total noise power ratio SNR; at the signal input of the device

$$\sigma_\gamma^2 = fg / (K \cdot 2^{r-1} \cdot \beta)$$

The value of β is given by A^2 / N_0 for narrow bandwidth noise and $\beta = B \sqrt{SNR}$ for wide bandwidth noise of bandwidth B much greater than signal frequency. Here A is the amplitude of the signal and N_0 is the spectral density of the noise near the signal frequency. As one may expect,

the value of σ_γ^2 is inversely proportional to τ .

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the device.

III. DIGITALLY CONTROLLED PHASE SHIFTER

A block scheme of the phase shifter is shown in Fig. 2. Both the input and output signals are rectangular waves. The frequency multiplier based on PLL produces a frequency that is $N = 256$ times greater than the frequency of the input signal f_s . Impulses of the frequency $N \cdot f_s$ are then counted by two down counters. Controlling bits are loaded to counter A during the positive edge of the input signal and to counter B during the negative edge of the input signal. If the controlling binary number is equal to M then the borrow impulse that sets the RS flip-flop delays by $M / (N f_s)$ with regard to the positive edge of the input signal. In the same way, the borrow impulse that resets the flip-flop delays by $M / (N f_s)$ with regard to the negative edge of the input signal. This corresponds to the phase shift of $M / N 360^\circ$ with the input signal shape preserved. Therefore, the phase shift may be controlled in the 0-3600 range and it is independent of the input signal frequency f_s .

The practical circuit was projected for other purposes and it allows a 7-bit phase control with 3° resolution rather than 8-bit control and 1.5° resolution, which may seem straightforward as $N = 256$. The frequency range of the device is 300 Hz to 15 kHz. It is necessary to stress that any frequency modulation of the PLL output causes errors in the phase shift so the loop filter must reject all ac components.

II MEASUREMENT

A sine reference signal of 1-kHz frequency was used in the experiment. It was fed directly to the reference input and through the variable phase shifter to the signal input. The signal at the latter input was mixed with the additive wide-bandwidth noise of bandwidth $\gg 1$ kHz. The generator frequency are varied from 500 Hz to 150 kHz. The signal to noise ratio SNR was also variable and reached -6 dB at minimum. Indications of the instrument were sensitive neither to changes of SNR nor to changes of f_g . The root mean square error of indications σ_γ is shown

in Fig. 3(b) against its values computed via (3). However, above a certain level of σ_γ (say 5°) the device became unstable and its indications showed large variations. This effect is most probably similar to the so-called cycle slipping in PLL's. However, the level of σ_γ at which it happens is somewhat small, so the reasons for this require further investigation.

Fig. 2. Digitally controlled phase shifter.

Fig. 3. (a) Acquisition time t_a against the generator frequency f_g . (b) Measured and computed values of σ_γ^2 .

The second measured parameter was the time of acquisition of the measured phase shift t_a which is defined as the time when $\Upsilon(t_a) = 0.1 \Upsilon_0$. It was measured for $\Upsilon_0 = 90^\circ$

The results are shown in Fig. 3(a). They agree well with the prediction $t_a = 2.2 \tau$. The increase of t_a for the smaller values of SNR is caused by the well-known degradation of

the triangle phase-detector characteristic for small SNR [9]. The precision of the measurements (~ 30) was determined by the resolution of the controlled phase shifter.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The device presented here makes possible precise phase measurements even in the presence of heavy noise interference in the signal channel. Its indications do not depend on the input signal frequency. The precision of the measurements is determined mainly by the resolution of the digitally controlled phase shifter. Improvement of the controlled phase shifter to provide better resolution is straightforward and a better precision of measurement may be readily obtained.

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